

THE PROJECT

The MAREWIND project provides vital solutions to help tackling the current challenges related to materials durability and maintenance in offshore wind energy structures. By enhancing the durability and recyclability of the materials and by improving the monitoring and reducing the maintenance in offshore structures, the project will contribute to a more economic and sustainable model of the offshore wind sector.

OBJECTIVES

MAREWIND targets the main aspects related to materials durability and maintenance in offshore structures which consequently imply failures, malfunctioning, loss of efficiency in energy generation and which have a major repercussion on O&M and CAPEX:

- enhancing corrosion protection systems and durability;
- effective and durable antifouling solutions without using biocides;
- erosion protection and mechanical reinforcement of wind blades;
- predictive modelling and monitoring; and
- increasing recyclability.

IMPACT

Economic & competitive innovative technology:

- improve performance and durability of materials at optimized costs; and
- reduce the life cycle costs and cost of the offshore energy production of about 40%.

Environmentally friendly benefits:

- reduce the environmental impact by 35%; and
- reduce CO₂ emissions and fuel dependency.

Socio-economic and development driven force:

- create growth and jobs in Europe; and
- strengthening the European industrial technology base.

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